

Influence use Media Learning Videoscribe to Results Study Students of SMPN 2 Rappang

Anwar^{1*}, Usman M², Nurzin R Kasau³, Syamsunir⁴, Sam Hermansyah⁵
Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidenreng Rappang
Corresponding Author: Anwar anwar@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The purposes of this research are to investigate:1) The differences in students learning outcomes between taught Videoscribe media and learning without Videoscribe media in class IX SMPN 2 Rappang. On chemical bonding materials 2) The influence of learning with Videoscribe media the learning outcomes in class IX SMPN 2 Rappang on chemical bonding material. The form of the research was quasy experiment with nonequivalent control group design. Sample selection technique was random sampling. The instrument of the research was of test. To find out the differences in student learning outcomes used the U-Mann Whitney test, based on the results of the hypothesis test obtained the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.033, the test results showed that there was a differences between students learning outcomes taught Videoscribe media and students learning outcomes taught without Videoscribe. Learning using Videoscribe learning media in class IX SMPN 2 Rappang on chemical bonding material giving the influence of 19.85% toward student learning outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Development knowledge knowledge And technology make student more Like Study with something new, easy and interesting like with see picture, videos or animation on tv , computers nor gadgets . Succeed or or not something learning No regardless of the way or method of teaching applied by Teacher in school. On presentation Geography lessons, a teacher needs to have appropriate teaching and learning strategies, so students are interested in studying Geography further (Ibrahim And Shaodih, 2010). If student have a high connection to learning, then he will try to prepare things related to what will be studied in a way better (Aunurahman, 2008).Teacher must use various approach, model, method And media learning so that learning objectives can be achieved held with effective And efficient so that obtained results Study Which in accordance with expectations. According to Azhar Arsyad (2002) in a learning process teacher inside class There is two element Which very important And each other related, that is method teaching And media learning. If something method that is used is appropriate and the use of the media teach that teachers use in the process Study teach appropriate, so matter the impact on enhancement performance Study student as well as can increase motivation Study student towards something lesson.

Based on the results of interviews with teachers Geography of SMPN 2 Rappang on date 1 August 2023 information was obtained that Teacher seldom use media in process learning, media learning Which Once used is type media visual that is power point Which only containing writing And picture simple And Teacher No Once use animation so that can make students are less interested, this is because because teachers are less skilled in making them other media. Several reasons why teachers rarely use media, including teachers No skilled use media learning, Teacher feel hassle If must use media learning in convey material, media learning Which Teacher want sometimes No available in school so teachers have to create media learning That Alone whereas time For make media That No Enough (Thomas Wibowo, 2005).Media learning in in process Study teach is factor important in support success something learning. Besides That use media can help task Teacher in convey lesson material through the media the containing ingredients Which must students learn so that students lack clarity to material Which Teacher explain can helped with exists media learning. Hamalik (2001) states that use media learning in process Study teaching can arouse desire and new interests, arouse motivation and stimulation activity Study, And even bring influences psychological to student. Besides awaken motivation And interest student, media learning Also can help student increase understanding, serve data with interesting And reliable, makes data interpretation easier, and compact information.

Based on the results of the questionnaire given to class X SMPN 2 Rappangpada date 1 August 2023 obtained information shows that students do not like it studying Geography, Geography lessons are considered difficult, method Teacher in teach not enough interesting, furthermore obtained information that student want there to be changes in Geography learning And student Like Study with animation. The low results Study student on eye

Geography lessons can be seen from test scores middle semester The low one i.e. average whole mark uts Geography class ! X SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL (48.7) Which has not yet reached the KKM (70). One of material lesson Geography on semester even SMPN 2 Rappang is bond Geography. Based on results interview with the Geography teacher at SMPN 2 Rappang material bond Geography is Wrong One examples of material that is difficult for students to understand Because material This nature abstract. According to Teacher Geography of SMPN 2 Rappang difficulties experienced student on material Geography that is they difficulty in understand process formation bond ion, bond covalent, differentiate between bond ion And bond covalent. Material bond Geography That difficult but draft bond Geography very important For mastered Because will used For study the material Geography other.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on description the, so an alternative is needed learning can used Teacher in teach Geography bond material. In delivering the material These Geography ties, teachers can use learning media for Geography related material more easy be delivered with clear And student become fast understand about material the media that can be used are: animation. Use media in learning can make it easier student in understanding something abstract becomes more concrete. Matter This in accordance with opinion Jerome S. Bruner that student Study through three stages that is enactive, iconic, and symbolic. The enactive stage is the stage where students learn with manipulate things concrete. The iconic stage is a stage where students Study with use picture or videotapes. Temporary stage symbolic that is stage Where student Study by using symbols (in Samsukur, 2013). Animation is a form of presentation the most interesting picture, which is in the form of simulation picture move Which describes displacement or movement an object (Mayer and Moreno in Ninuk, 2014). Use animation in process learning very help in increase effectiveness And efficiency process learning. Animation also can increase Power pull student in follow the learning process. The animation can used in process learning that is Videoscribe. Videoscribe is is multimedia based computer, form audio visual in form animation with images and narrated or better known text with keyboard animation.

Irwan Adimas Double Saputra (2023) state that the advantage of audiovisual media is that it can describe imagination participant educate, And can repeated when need For add clarity. On use media learning Videoscribe This so process learning become more Manarik And attention student more focused on material. Djamarah And Zain (in Ninuk, 2014) state that benefit or values Which caused from use media animation in process Study teach are; a) animation media can help students in study a very wide range of study materials, Which where in inside load various type draft, fact, And principles certain Which relate with material the lesson; b) animation media can also be used assist a teacher in delivering material his learning in class; c) media animation can increase satisfaction And success Study student in accordance with desire each Teacher; d) media animation can increase performance Study,

attitude And method Study his students feel satisfied And succeed with process learning; e) mediaanimation can increase performance Study, effective student attitudes and ways of learning as well grow perception Which tall to things that studied.

METHODOLOGY

Form study This is Quasy Experimental Design or experiment pseudo. Population in study This is student class IX SMPN 2 Rappang Year Teachings 2022/2023 which consists of 2 classes. Test results homogeneity on population show that second class homogeneous, so that used random sampling. Class IX is selected as class Control And class IX as class experiment. Design study as follows:

Table 1. Nonequivalent Control Group Design n

<i>Pretest</i>	<i>Class</i>	<i>Posttest</i>	<i>Treatment</i>
O 1		X	O 2
Experiment			
Control	O 3	-	O 4

Information:

- O 1 : Pretest on class experiment
- O 3 : Pretest in class control
- X : Treatment on class experiment
- O 2 : Posttest in the experimental class
- O 4 : Posttest on control class

Stage Preparation Study

Steps Which done in preparation stages include: (1) Carrying out pre-research in SMPN 2 Rappang. (2) Formulate problem. (3) Preparation Learning. (4) Compile device learning form Plan Implementation Learning (RPP), test question grid, rubric evaluation along with guidelines scoring. (5) Do validation instrument And device learning form question test, media Videoscribe learning and lesson plans to one person lecturer FKIP UMS Rappang And One person Teacher Geography SMPN 2 Rappang. (6) Improving research instruments based on results validation. (7) Do test try research instrument based on results validation. (8) Analyze data results test try For know level reliability Sidrap instrument. Reliability test calculated with use formula alpha as following:stages include: (1) Providing pretest class experiment And class control For know ability beginning student to material before given treatment. (2) Carry out process learning using Videoscribe learning media on class experiment with and carry out learning without using Videoscribe learning media class control. (3) Give posttest on class experiment and class control with the aim is to find out the results student learning after given treatment.

Stage End Study

Steps Which done in Implementation stages include: (1) carry out analysis And processing data results study on class control And class experiment use test statistics Which in accordance, (2) make discussion And

conclusion from results study, (3) compile report study. The measurement techniques used in This research is a way of collecting data done with with Good form tool specifically made for that purpose (Hadari Nawawi, 2012). Technique measurement in study This that is giving test. Tool collector data Which used in This research is a test. Tests used in this research are pre-test and post- test.

Validity test Which used in study This is validity content, Where carried out with expert judgment by people The expert, in this case is a Geography lecturer and Teacher eye lesson Geography SMPN 2 Rappang. Influence use media learning Videoscribe to results Study student class I _ on material bond Geography SMPN 2 Rappang can be calculated using effect size with the formula:

$$\delta = \frac{\bar{Y}_e - \bar{Y}_c}{S_c}$$

After obtained mark ICE so mark the entered to in table wide in lower standard normal curvature O to Z Then times 100% so that obtained percentage enhancement results Study Because influence use media learning Videoscribe to results Study student class X on material bond Geography Senior High School Sidrap.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mark pretest obtained from results giving question test before treatment on class experimental and control classes, while the value The posttest is obtained from the results of giving test questions after given treatment on class experiment and control class. Based on results pretest on Table 2 shows that there is not a single student who achieved completion of KKM 75, both students class control nor class experiment. Matter the because Good class control nor class experiment not yet given treatment. However, after given treatment which different, obtained difference between mark flat- control class average with the class average value experiment.

After given treatment on class experimental and control classes of students were given posttest questions are intended to find out results Study Geography student. If seen from completeness, many student which complete in the experimental class than in the control class. Students do not complete due to There are some students who pay less attention when the teacher explain nor broadcast material with Videoscribe . From learning results which obtained from second class, can observed comparison of pretest and posttest scores. Results Study student class experiment more Good compared to student learning outcomes control class. Comparison mark average results Study class experiment which taught use media learning Videoscribe with results Study student class control Which taught without use media learning Videoscribe can be in Look on Figure 1.

Table 2. Results Pretest and Class Posttest Control and Class Experiment

Class	Pretest		Posttest	
	Average	% completeness	Average	% completeness
Class Control	28.43	0	61.28	21.87
Class Experiment	29.58	0	70.42	38.70

Based on Picture 1, on class control happen enhancement results Study amounted to 32.85 and in the experimental class happen enhancement results Study as big as 40.57. On posttest happen enhancement completeness student, average mark posttest students in the experimental class were larger namely 70.42 than the control class, namely amounting to 61.28. Judging from the average results student learning and learning completion, on class experiment more tall from on class control.

Initial Abilities of Control Class Students and Experimental Class

Results Study which moreover formerly processed is pretest from class control and experiment which aim for know There is or not difference students' initial abilities in both classes the before given treatment. The processing of pretest results can be explained as following: Test Normality and Homogeneity Mark Pretest. Results test the pretest normality obtained Sig value at test Kolmogorov-Smirnov on class control as big as 0,000 and on class experiment obtained mark Sig as big as 0,000. A data is said to be distributed normal If mark sig > 0 .05 . Results test normality mark pretest class control not normally distributed because $0.000 < 0.05$, and results test normality class experiment distributed No normal Because $0,000 < 0.05$. Furthermore done test Homogeneity (Levene's Test), obtained information that data on second group own variant Which No the same, meaning the sample has the same data not homogeneous with the Sig value. $0.001 < 0 .05$.

Figure 1. Mark average Pretest-Posttest Class Control and Experimental Class

Based on results test precondition in on, so for know difference students' initial abilities used the U- test Mann whitney. Hypothesis Testing, based on the results of the test hypothesis with a sig value of $0.289 > 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected. So, can concluded that No there is difference ability beginning student class control and class experiment.

Control Class Student Learning Results and Class Experiment

Test normality posttest, result test normality posttest obtained mark Sig on test Kolmogorov-Smirnov on class control as big as 0.011 and on class experiment obtained mark Sig as big as 0.026. A data is said to be distributed normal If mark sig > 0.05 . Results test normality mark posttest class control No normally distributed because $0.011 < 0.05$. Whereas, results test normality class experiment No distribute normal because $0.026 < 0.05$. Furthermore done test Homogeneity (Levene's Test), obtained information that data on second group own variant Which No the same, meaning the sample has the same data not homogeneous with the Sig value. $0.001 < 0.05$. Based on results test precondition in on, so for know difference students' final abilities used the U- test Mann Whitney.

Influence Use Media Videoscribe to Results Study Student

Application media learning Videoscribe give influence to results Study student, For know how much big its influence The effect size calculation is carried out , where obtained mark effect size as big as 0.58 with criteria currently. Mark effect size The results obtained are then interpreted on on barometer Hattie so that Information was obtained that the effect size value enter into the Zone of desires effects Which meaning that treatment influence learning outcomes or increasing learning outcomes student influenced by media The learning provided is media learning Videoscribe . Then For know big percentage influence so mark effect size interpreted in the extensive table below curved normal O to Z Then multiplied 100% so that information obtained that learning with Videoscribe media is making an impact as big as 19.85% to enhancement results Study student.

Based on analysis data enhancement the learning outcomes of experimental class students are more larger than the control class. Difference results Study students on both class This caused by different treatments in the process learning in two class the. On class experiment taught with media learning Videoscribe while the control class was taught without use media learning Videoscribe. Experimental class is better from class control caused class experiment taught use media learning Videoscribe. Media learning is used for convey material on class experiment. Delivery material on class control done with method conventional that is with method lecture without use media learning Videoscribe. There is three steps taken by the teacher in process learning with model conventional, namely introduction, activities core and cover. Classroom learning experiment Also there is three step Which done by Teacher in process learning, namely introduction, activities core And closing. Same case with control class, all three steps are in in learning conventional Also

done by Teacher on class experiment. The difference only lies on activity core. On class control delivery material without use videoscribe whereas on class experiment delivery material with using videoscribe.

Activity core class control on meeting 1 discussed ionic bonds And on meeting 2 discuss about bond covalent. Learning on activity core, first of all Teacher explain material about bond ion. After finished convey material, Teacher give chance to student For ask, And There is student Which asked because he was still confused about method something element For stable Then Teacher answered question the. Next, the teacher gives example questions which is done by involving students so that teachers can know as far as possible material that students understand. Then teacher provide practice questions to work on by student. Giving question exercise this intended so that Teacher Can see so far where level understanding student about material which has be delivered. Teacher Give time for students to answer question exercise the. Then Teacher request student proceed to front for write the answer in board write. Then teacher and student which other correct and discuss the results of the work student Which There is in board write. With Having these practice questions will motivate you students that the learning is carried out not just for fun, but really- Correct For increase results Study student. Closing, on activity This Teacher together student make conclusion to material which be delivered.

Learning in the experimental class on activity core Teacher broadcast material with Videoscribe And student notice videos the, on meeting First Teacher broadcast material about bond ion And on meeting second Teacher broadcast material about bond covalent, student seen very enthusiastic notice videos And Teacher supervise student so that notice videos, However there is a number of student Which is at behind seen not enough pay attention And chat with her friend soteacher approach And rebuked him so that notice. After Videoscribe shown by the teacher asking students about understanding and the process of forming bonds Geography part big student can answer And Then Teacher give explanation more carry on. Then Teacher give students the opportunity to ask about material which not enough clear And There is a student ask How For determine mark electonegativity something element Then Teacher explain that every element each has its own electronegativity value. Each of which can be seen in the value table electronegativity element. Furthermore Teacher give question exercise for done. Then the teacher asked for one student proceed forward For do practice questions on the blackboard, at meetings First there is 2 person student Which work on questions on the blackboard and on The second meeting contained 3 students Which do question in board write. Then Teacher and student which ain correct And discuss results which has written on the blackboard. Next stage closing, Teacher guide student for conclude material which has studied.

Based on observations during the process learning in class, student class experiment Which taught use media learning Videoscribe more easy in absorb And understand lesson Because with media learning can interesting attention student, seen moment Teacher give question nor conclude lesson, student class experiment more active in answer than class control. Media learning

Videoscribe more interesting for student, Because student involved active in the learning so that student No bored And enthusiastic from on learning with method lecture on class control, seen moment in the classroom learning process experiment more Lots Which ask than the control class

Media learning Videoscribe too can increase Power pull student in follow the learning process. Learning with media Videoscribe can increase description imagination participant educate, And can repeated when need for add clarity so that student can learn return material which has taught with twist Videoscribe learning media at home. With learning media Videoscribe which can display information through voice, picture, movement And the color of the subject matter which is packaged through media will more clear, complete, as well as interesting interest student. With media, material dish can awaken flavor curiosity student and stimulate student react both physically and _ emotional. In short, media learning can help Teacher for creating a learning atmosphere does watch And No boring, process learning become more interactive. In general, the benefits of media learning Videoscribe This in process learning is smooth interaction between teachers and student so that learning will more effective And efficient so that learning Which Teacher give more easy For delivered And achieved objective learning. Use media learning Videoscribe can increase results Study student in accordance with theory from Arsyad Which state that use of media-based learning Videoscribe which is integrated from words and picture Which can communicate elements knowledge with that way organized with Good, Specific, And clear can increase results Study student. Superiority use media learning Videoscribe means you can create activities learning become more interesting students' attention, students become more active ask And answer question Teacher.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on analysis data Which done, so can concluded that: (1) There is difference results Study student Class IX SMPN 2 Rappang Antara Which taught with use media learning Videoscribe with learning without use media learning Videoscribe . (2) Learning with learning media Videoscribe give influence as big as 19.85 % towards increasing learning outcomes student Based on results study Which done, there is a number of suggestion Which can researcher give, that is : (1) For Teacher Which want to use media learning Videoscribe expected notice suitability material Which will be delivered. (2) For researchers who want to use media learning Videoscribe can use material different and make improvements study previously And should test try it moreover formerly media This learning is so that students can be immersed in it follow the learning process.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on the topic "Influence use Media Learning Videoscribe to Results Study Students of SMPN 2 Rappang."

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